

Regular article

Dissolved CO₂ profile in bio-succinic acid production from sugars-rich industrial waste

Francesco Vigato, Irini Angelidaki, John M. Woodley, Merlin Alvarado-Morales*

Chemical and Biochemical Engineering Department, DTU, Køgens Lyngby, Denmark

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Succinic acid
Carbon dioxide
Actinobacillus succinogenes
Waste valorization

ABSTRACT

The inorganic carbon source (CO₂) availability to the microorganisms has a key role in the succinic acid (SA) fermentation process. This study aims to investigate the behavior of the inorganic carbon source for SA production and underline the importance of CO₂ in the fermentation process. The effect of pressure was investigated for CO₂ availability and its overall impact on the fermentation process. Results obtained demonstrated a significant effect of pressure on yield, productivity and CO₂ fixation rate. Industrial waste, rich in maltose, glucose, and sucrose, was used as feedstock combined with a gas mixture of CH₄ and CO₂, which simulated biogas composition. A final titer for succinic acid of 25.5 ± 2.4 g/L was detected at a headspace gas pressure of 1.4 atm. The yield raised from 0.48 g/g sugars to 0.64 and 0.65 g/g sugars when 1.4 and 1.6 atm pressure was applied, respectively. Overall, this study represents one of the first attempts to explore CO₂ availability during succinic acid production, using biogas as a CO₂ source and sugars-rich industrial waste as feedstock.

1. Introduction

Succinic acid (SA) can both be produced through petrochemical and fermentation processes. The fermentation-based process consists of the biochemical reaction between the organic and inorganic (CO₂) carbon sources to form the biobased succinic acid or bio-succinic acid. When bio-succinic acid is obtained, CO₂ is consumed with obvious advantages compared to the petrochemical route.

The inorganic carbon source can be provided both as salts (MgCO₃, NaHCO₃) or in the gaseous form (CO₂). Carbon dioxide plays a crucial role during microbial fermentation since it is necessary to control the carbon flux to the succinic acid route (C4 pathway) and reduce by-products formation (C3 pathway) [1,2]. Several studies provided the inorganic carbon by adding salts, (*i.e.* MgCO₃ or NaHCO₃) to the fermentation medium [3,4] with the advantage to make it directly available in the liquid phase but with the necessity to remove the left-over when the fermentation is completed. In contrast, when CO₂ is fed as gas, it must be firstly dissolved in the fermentation medium to be utilized by the bacteria. Once in the liquid phase, this molecule reacts with water to form, at fermentation pH, the bicarbonate ion (HCO₃⁻). Then it permeates through the cell membrane and takes part in the internal metabolic pathways of the specific microorganisms. In anaerobic conditions with *Actinobacillus succinogenes* 130Z [5–7], the inorganic carbon

reacts with PEP-carboxykinase (Fig. 1), the key enzyme that converts PEP into oxaloacetate, and consequently directs the carbon flux towards the C4 pathway. PEP carboxykinase has a low affinity to CO₂ with the consequent increase in its binding capacity, and high half saturation constant (K_s), with the inorganic molecule. Pyruvate kinase instead binds PEP (Fig. 1) to direct the carbon flux to the production of acetic acid, formic acid, and ethanol as final products [8]. Consequently, to further increase carbon flux through the C4 pathway (Fig. 1), the availability of inorganic carbon has a fundamental contribution to the activation of PEP carboxykinase which is a crucial node when the desired final product is SA [9,10].

As 1 mol of CO₂ is theoretically required for the synthesis of 1 mol of succinic acid, providing the correct amount of CO₂ is important to improve succinic acid production maximizing gas consumption [11]. Moreover, higher availability of CO₂ to the cells could lead to the reduction of by-products formation and an increase in succinic acid titer and yield [12–14]. Lastly, providing CO₂ from industrial streams or CO₂-rich streams *e.g.* biogas can have the extra benefit to reduce the concentration of the CO₂ and consequently obtained a stream with high biomethane (≥ 95% v/v).

For these reasons, to enhance the consumption of CO₂ during the fermentation process, gas partial pressure, hydration reactions and gas-liquid mass transfer must be examined. When CO₂ is provided as mixed

* Correspondence to: Department of Chemical and Biochemical Engineering, Technical University of Denmark, DK-2800 Køgens Lyngby, Denmark.

E-mail address: meal@kt.dtu.dk (M. Alvarado-Morales).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2022.108602>

Received 16 May 2022; Received in revised form 5 August 2022; Accepted 22 August 2022

Available online 27 August 2022

1369-703X/© 2022 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Fig. 1. *Actinobacillus succinogenes* simplified metabolic pathway. Succinic acid is produced as main product in the C4 pathway. 1: Membrane transport systems; 2: Embden-Meyerhof pathway enzymes; 3: Malate dehydrogenase; 4: fumarase; 5: fumarate reductase; 6: malic enzyme; 7: pyruvate kinase; 8: lactate dehydrogenase; 9: pyruvate–formate lyase; 10: acetate kinase and phosphotransacetylase; 11: acetaldehyde dehydrogenase and alcohol dehydrogenase. Image based on Cheng et al., 2012 [7].

gas particular interest must be given to the partial pressure of the considered gas. The control and increase of the CO_2 partial pressure, as described by Henry's law, lead to the increase in the dissolved concentration of the same compound [14,15]. Besides, the transport across the gas-liquid interface is regulated by the $k_L a$, influenced by system design and the process parameters (Supplementary materials, Section 1.1). Lastly, once the CO_2 is dissolved in the fermentation medium, the microbial uptake influences its concentration by the consumption and fixation in the form of SA. Even if inorganic carbon has a key role in the production of SA (Fig. 1), only a few articles investigated the simultaneous consumption of organic and inorganic carbon sources during fermentation [9,15,16].

Similar to the CO_2 role in biosuccinic acid production, the organic carbon sources can have an important part in the cost reduction of the fermentation-based process. Organic carbon consists of a wide range of sugars both in the form of pure compounds or as mixed sugars from biomass and waste materials. The conversion of waste or low-value materials into this dicarboxylic acid has been successfully achieved in the past [17–20] opening several possibilities of feedstocks selection for its fermentation route. Moreover, many other chemicals and fuels have been obtained from residual or waste feedstock such as bioethanol, derived from biomass feedstock [21], lactic acid [22], biobutanol [23, 24], and sophorolipid [25], to demonstrate the valorization of many waste products as a carbon source for the production of value-added compounds.

In the present study, sugars-rich industrial wastes and high CO_2 -containing gas streams were fermented with *A. succinogenes* to produce SA. One example of sugar-rich industrial waste is a sidestream from candy factories that are often delivered to biogas plants. At the moment, this sugars-rich industrial waste has low commercial value, and disposal of this waste can be an expense for the factories. Alternatively, this sugars-rich industrial waste can be used for the production of SA with obvious advantages. The combination of cheap sugars-rich industrial waste with biogas (a mix of CH_4 and CO_2 60/40% v/v [26]) can contribute to lowering the production costs for the SA production process and make it competitive against its petrochemical counterpart.

To investigate the role of CO_2 during succinic acid production, *Actinobacillus succinogenes* 130Z was chosen as a model organism. Moreover, its ability to grow on a wide range of C5 and C6 substrates with the formation of biosuccinic acid as the main product makes this bacterium appropriate to investigate the fermentation process with the sugars-rich industrial residues [17,27,28].

Thus, this study investigated the behavior of carbon dioxide during SA production from sugars-rich industrial waste in a fermentation batch system. The role of CO_2 during SA fermentation was deeply studied and presented to further increase the knowledge about the co-consumption of organic and inorganic carbon sources. Thereafter, the application of a CO_2 -rich stream like biogas was tested to demonstrate the suitability of the fermentation process as an upgrade system for the added production of high in purity methane.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Substrate, chemicals, and gases collection and preparation

All the gas utilized was supplied by AGA A/S Copenhagen, Denmark. A mix of CH_4 and CO_2 was collected from pressurized bottles and transferred into sealed plastic bags. Gas was injected into the fermentors by sterile tubes (Saint-Gobain Pharmed® BPT). All chemicals used in this study were of analytical grade and purchased from Sigma-Aldrich ApS (Brøndby, Denmark). Sugars-rich industrial waste was provided by Trollic Ibérica, SA C/ Bombers 22, Tactical Business Park (Paterna, Spain). The initial concentration of sugars obtained from the carbohydrates analysis ranges between 276.6 ± 2.7 and 306.9 ± 5.7 g/L. The substrates were diluted (2:1 sugars-rich industrial waste: water) and with distilled water, homogenized, and stored in a -20°C freezer before use.

2.2. Microorganism, and microbial cultivation

As model microorganism *Actinobacillus succinogenes* 130Z (DSMZ 22257) was used. The stock culture was stored in glycerol at -80°C before use. Seed culture was prepared according to Marinho et al. [17]. Seed media composition consists of (g/L): glucose (10.0), yeast extract (5.0), NaHCO_3 (10.0), $\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (9.6), $\text{K}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (20.3). Nitrogen (N_2) gas was used to establish anaerobic conditions in 50 mL sealed anaerobic bottles (SABs) filled with 30 mL of fermentation medium. The medium was sterilized at 121°C for 20 min and then cultivated at 37.5°C and shaken at 150 rpm for 48 h in a shaking incubator (IKA® KS4000i control). A volume of 1.0 mL glycerol stock was used to inoculate the sterile bottles.

2.3. Batch fermentations in 200 mL bottles

Batch fermentations were conducted in duplicates in 200 mL sealed anaerobic bottles with 100 mL initial working volume. The final performance was reported in terms of final succinic acid titer (g/L), succinic acid productivity (SA_p - g/Lh), and succinic acid yield as grams of succinic acid produced (g) per 1 g of total sugars consumed as follows:

$$Y_{\text{SA}/\text{TS}} = \frac{C_{\text{SA}} - C_{\text{SA}}^0}{C_{\text{TS}}^0 - C_{\text{TS}}}$$

$$\text{SA}_p = \frac{\Delta C_{\text{SA}}}{\Delta t}$$

Where C_{SA} and C_{TS} are the concentration of SA and total sugars at the end of the fermentation (g/L), while C_{SA}^0 and C_{TS}^0 the concentration of SA and total sugars at the start of the fermentation (g/L).

Media were prepared as follows (g/L): yeast extract (10.0), K_2HPO_4 (3.0), MgCl_2 (0.2), CaCl_2 (0.2), NaCl (1.0), MgCO_3 . Magnesium carbonate was estimated based on the initial organic carbon concentration

[29]. When 20 g/L of total initial sugars were tested, MgCO_3 was set to 40 g/L. However, for 40 and 60 g/L of total initial sugars, the MgCO_3 was set to 80 g/L. This was to ensure no limitation of inorganic carbon in the fermentation media. The culture medium was autoclaved at 121 °C for 20 min. The sugars-rich industrial waste solutions (20, 40, and 60 g/L) were added with a sterile filter (0.22 μm) and mixed with the synthetic medium at a 75:25 ratio (medium:substrate). The pH was adjusted to 6.75 either with 50 % phosphoric acid H_3PO_4 or 8.0 M NaOH. The bottles were inoculated with 10% (v/v) exponential phase inoculum under anaerobic conditions by N_2 flushed in the media. Fermentation was conducted for 24 h at 37.5 °C at 150 rpm in a shaking incubator (IKA® KS4000i control). A pure solution of glucose was used as the positive control with an initial concentration of 20 g/L. Samples were collected every hour for the first three hours, then every hour and a half and stored at – 20 °C before analysis.

2.4. Batch fermentations in 3 L fermentors

The batch fermentations were performed using two identical 3-L Sartorius Biostat A-Plus fermenters (Fig. 2). Similar to serum anaerobic bottle fermentation, media were prepared with the same concentration of nutrients. The inorganic carbon source was supplied by sparging the liquid with gaseous CO_2 during all the fermentation as presented in the system in Fig. 2. The CO_2 was recirculated in the fermentation by a peristaltic pump (Watson-Marlow, United Kingdom) and the gas flow rate was set at 0.73 L/min (0.4 vvm). The gas was sparged through the gas inlet after filtration with a sterile filter (0.22 μm) and bubbled into the media from the sparger at the bottom of the reactors to dissolve the CO_2 in the liquid. Thereafter, the gas was recirculated from the outlet to the gas bag (Fig. 2). The headspace pressure was set at 1.0, 1.4, and 1.6 atm (Fig. 2) in the outlet tube by FESTO gauges.

The media to substrate ratio was maintained at 75:25 with an initial working volume of 1.8 L. Fermenters were inoculated with 10% (v/v) exponential phase inoculum. A volume of 13.4 L of CO_2 was required with 70 g/L of sugars, however, since the system was operated with a biogas mixture (40 % CO_2), the total volume of biogas required for the fermentation was calculated to be 36.0 L (Supporting material). The temperature was raised to 37.5 °C by the heating jacket, pH was automatically adjusted along all the fermentation by the control unit to 6.75. NaOH 8.0 M solution was used to control the pH and added automatically during the fermentation. The sugars-rich industrial wastes used as

feedstock were added after pasteurization at 80 °C for 15 min. The anaerobic condition was created by flushing with nitrogen. The initial concentration of sugars ranged between 60 and 70 g/L. Thus, the corresponding volume of CO_2 was collected. Gas was analyzed frequently by gas-chromatography with TDC detection. For chemical analysis of fermentation products and sugars, samples were collected frequently from the sampler port and stored in a – 20 °C freezer until use. Fermentations were run for a total of 24 h. The fermented broth and the remaining gas were collected and stored in a 5-L plastic tank for further analysis.

During the fermentation, pH probes InPro3253i/225 (Mettler Toledo, Denmark), temperature probe (Sartorius, Germany), and CO_2 sensor InPro5000i/12/220 were mounted to the 3-L Sartorius metal head for online recording. Online pH measurement was collected by the Sartorius MSDA program and dissolved CO_2 concentration by M800 Mettler Toledo transmitter. For each operating pressure control experiment (without inoculation) was conducted. Control experiments data were used to calculate the gas-liquid mass transfer coefficient ($k_L a$ [h^{-1}]) and the Henry constant (H [$\text{kPa}\cdot\text{L}/\text{mol}$]).

2.5. Analytical methods

Sugar composition was measured by Dionex ICS-6000 DC. The column used for the analysis was a Carpac Pa20 with a mixed eluent of 10–200 mM NaOH. ICS eluent flow and the temperature was set to 0.4 mL/min at 30 °C for 35 min. Fermentation products were collected and analyzed by HPLC Shimadzu Nexera XR with HPLC Organic Acid Analysis Column Aminex® HPX-87H Ion Exclusion Column. Eluent for the analysis was H_2SO_4 12 mM. Micro-Guard Cation H^+ Refill Cartridges were supplied by Bio-Rad and used as pre-column.

HPLC analysis was carried on at 64 °C for 25 min. Eluent flow was stabilized at 0.6 mL/min. The gas analysis was conducted by Thermo-fisher Trace 1310 Gas Chromatography. OD_{630} was measured to the characterized bacterial growth curve. Shimadzu UV-1280 UV-Vis spectrophotometer was used for the purpose. Hydrochloric acid was used when needed to neutralize the MgCO_3 effect during growth curve analysis.

2.6. Statistical methods

An ANOVA analysis followed by Fisher's Least Significant Difference test (LSD, $p < 0.05$) was conducted to validate any significant

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the fermentation setup. Batch fermentation is conducted in a 3 L vessel. The gas is recirculated by peristaltic pump, previous to filtration with sterile filter. The gas is sparged from the sparger at the bottom of the reactor and, by the outlet, the pressure is control.

Fig. 3. Growth curve (A), Succinic acid (B), Acetate (C), and Formic acid (D) for SABs fermentations. Fermentation tests were conducted with increasing initial total sugars concentrations: 20 g/L (●), 40 g/L (▲), and 60 g/L (▼). Glucose 20 g/L was investigated as positive control (■). Cell growth is counted as cell dry weight (CDW).

differences between the experimental results. Statistical analyses were performed using OriginPro 2021 Software (OriginLab Corporation, Northampton, MA).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Succinic acid production on sealed anaerobic bottles

Preliminary tests were conducted in sealed bottles to elucidate the effect of sugar-rich industrial wastes, at different concentrations, on microbial growth and succinic acid production. Batches with 20 g/L glucose as the only substrate were also tested as a control, to compare microbial performance with the industrial substrate. The initial concentration of total sugars ranged between 20 and 60 g/L. After inoculation, 10 h of exponential phase cell growth was observed, whereafter, cells entered the stationary phase. As expected, the metabolites SA, acetic acid (AA), and formic acid (FA) were formed at similar rates as the cell biomass increased rates during the exponential growth phase (Fig. 3B, C, D). The profile of growth is presented in Fig. 3A indicating a consistent ability of *A. succinogenes* to metabolize the sugars-rich industrial waste. Lag-phase was not observed in the present study.

Fermentation data are summarised in Table 1. The highest SA titer was 22.6 ± 0.5 g/L obtained with 40 g/L initial sugars concentration. Yield and productivity reached 0.64 ± 0.07 gSA/g-sugars and 0.94 ± 0.04 g/L-h respectively. When 60 g/L was the initial total sugar concentration, the process performance significantly deteriorated. The yield obtained was only about 0.36 ± 0.04 gSA/g-sugars with 16.3

± 1.3 g/L of sugars not consumed after 24 h. These results suggest that under these conditions the upper sugar concentration permitted is below 60 g/L due to pH drop as a consequence of acid formation. Higher sugar levels will significantly limit process performance. No ethanol or lactic acid was observed during the bottle tests.

3.2. Succinic acid production in 3 L fermentors

Based on the results from the bottle tests, fermentations were carried out in 3 L fermentors for 24 h to determine experimental conditions to improve the fermentation performance. At the upscaled fermentation, the initial total sugar concentration was increased ranging from 60 to 70 g/L, SABs upper limit concentration. The initial heterogeneity and viscosity of the sugars-rich industrial waste made it difficult to fix the initial sugar concentration on a specific level. Biomass generation, fermentation products, and sugar consumption are shown in Fig. 4. From 1.0–1.4 and from 1.0 to 1.6 a significant increase in titer was observed ($p < 0.05$). Besides, yield was significantly different from 1.0 to 1.4 atm and from 1.0 to 1.6 atm with a 0.64 ± 0.06 and 0.65 ± 0.09 gSA/g-sugars yield ($p < 0.05$). The higher yield at 1.4 atm compared to 1.0 atm was due to higher inorganic carbon availability resulting in higher metabolites production. Biomass concentration increased from 4.66 gDW/L in 1.0 atm batch to 6.65 and 5.88 gDW/L in 1.4 atm and 1.6 atm respectively when bacterial cells entered the stationary phase.

A slight decrease of biomass was detected at 24 h in the pressurized system. This decrease can be explained by the increase of Na^+ ions to

Table 1

Microbial performance in SA production with the different experimental setups. Fermentation was conducted at 37.5 °C for 24 h. The pH was adjusted to 6.75. Headspace pressure was controlled in the 3-L fermentation process and set at 1.0, 1.4 and 1.6 atm.

	Initial sugars	Succinic acid	Acetic acid	Formic acid	Lactic acid	Ethanol	Yield	Productivity	Leftover sugars
	(g/L)	(g/L)	(g/L)	(g/L)	(g/L)	(g/L)	g/g sugars	g·L ⁻¹ ·h ⁻¹	(g/L)
SAB_glucose	21.5 ± 1.5	12.5 ± 0.7	5.2 ± 0.3	4.4 ± 0.1	–	–	0.58	0.52	0.2 ± 0.0
SAB_20	23.7 ± 0.6	16.1 ± 0.3	9.4 ± 0.3	6.9 ± 0.1	–	–	0.71	0.67	1.1 ± 0.1
SAB_40	36.2 ± 1.4	22.6 ± 0.5	11.4 ± 0.3	9.5 ± 0.2	–	–	0.64	0.94	1.0 ± 0.0
SAB_60	62.8 ± 2.9	17.1 ± 1.2	6.4 ± 0.1	7.2 ± 0.1	–	–	0.36	0.71	16.3 ± 1.3
Sart_Glu	40.2 ± 0.0	18.0 ± 0.1	9.3 ± 0.4	9.4 ± 0.9	–	–	0.51	0.75	4.4 ± 0.02
1.0 atm	65.8 ± 4.1	20.3 ± 1.3	8.4 ± 0.5	6.8 ± 0.8	3.2 ± 0.9	1.9 ± 0.6	0.48	0.85	23.6 ± 0.3
1.4 atm	60.8 ± 2.3	25.5 ± 2.4	10.2 ± 0.1	7.2 ± 0.1	2.6 ± 1.7	2.9 ± 0.5	0.64	1.06	20.9 ± 2.7
1.6 atm	70.3 ± 2.8	23.9 ± 2.7	9.9 ± 0.4	8.0 ± 1.2	4.0 ± 3.7	2.2 ± 0.0	0.65	0.99	33.3 ± 5.3

control the pH, with the subsequent rise of the osmotic stress on the cells [9].

Sugars consumption is shown in Fig. 4(B-D-F). The sugars-rich industrial waste used as feedstock was composed of maltose, glucose, and sucrose (Table 2). When the initial sugar concentration was 60–70 g/L approx. 25 g/L sugars were at average leftover at the end of the fermentation time, mainly maltose and a trace amount of glucose from disaccharides hydrolysis. It is worth noticing that by comparing results at upscaled fermentations to the previous at a smaller scale, a significant improvement of microbial performance on yield, titer and productivity was achieved at initial sugar concentrations higher than 60 g/L ($p < 0.05$).

Furthermore, by analyzing the gas composition in the headspace, a significant decrease in CO₂ content along with an increase in pressure was observed from 1.0 to 1.4 and 1.6 atm ($p < 0.05$; Table 3). At 1.0 atm the final concentration of CO₂ in the gas bag achieved only 33.8 ± 0.9% v/v, in contrast at 1.4 and 1.6 atm higher upgrade was noticed leading to the final values of 19.6 ± 2.6 and 17.3 ± 5.6% v/v ($p < 0.05$). Similar results have been previously observed highlighting a significant improvement in CO₂ fixation at higher pressures. Gunnarsson et al. [15] obtained a CO₂ composition of 4.6 % and 8.9% v/v when pressure increased from 40% v/v initial concentration.

The higher consumption of HCO₃⁻ dissolved from 1.0 to 1.4 ($p < 0.05$) and 1.0–1.6 ($p < 0.05$) atm corresponded to higher final SA titer, yield, and productivity due to higher availability of the bicarbonate ions along the microbial exponential phase. A complete mass balance for the CO₂ is presented in the Supporting material.

3.3. Microbial performance

The improved performance was obtained when the fermentation was upscaled to 1.8 L working volume which could be operated in a controlled environment. *A. succinogenes* was able to grow in presence of all the different sugars (glucose, sucrose, and maltose) contained in the substrate. It has been previously reported that *A. succinogenes* has a broad substrate preference [10,32]. In Fig. 4B, D, and F maltose is the main leftover sugar after 24 h of fermentation. Only when sucrose and glucose are fully consumed (Fig. 4B, C, D 9 h), the bacteria start consuming maltose. The residual maltose concentration and the preferred consumption of glucose and sucrose by *Actinobacillus succinogenes* can be explained by intracellular transport mechanisms. Glucose and sucrose are imported with the phosphotransferase transport system where the transport into the cytoplasm is directly linked with the phosphorylation into Glucose-6-phosphate and Fructose-6-phosphate [32,33]. However, the conversion of sucrose by *A. succinogenes* needs the breaking of the α -1, β -2-glycosidic linkage before the consumption of the single monomers with the consequent increase in the energy demand for the reaction [34,35]. Moreover, maltose is characterized by an

ATP-dependent transport system that additionally increases the consumption of energy by the bacteria [32].

Fermentation under controlled conditions resulted in improved yield and productivity. When the pressure was increased to 1.4 atm and 1.6 atm, the final yield observed was 0.64 ± 0.06 and 0.65 ± 0.09 gSA/g sugars, respectively, which was significantly different from the 1.0 atm test ($p < 0.05$). Results are in line with the literature applying similar conditions. Gunnarsson et al. [15] reported, at 1.4 atm and 30 g/L glucose concentration, a final yield of 0.62 and 0.63 gSA/g sugars, higher respect 1.0 atm. Similarly, Amulya et al. [36] obtained the highest titer of succinic acid at 2 bar (14.86 g/L). Productivity results indicate a similar trend, when pressure is raised from 1.0 atm to 1.4 and 1.6 atm, a consequent increase in productivity ($p < 0.05$) is observed increasing from 0.85 ± 0.07–1.06 ± 0.03 and 0.99 ± 0.04 g·L⁻¹·h⁻¹.

In addition to acetic acid and formic acid, at the beginning of the stationary phase (Figs. 4, 7.5 h), ethanol was formed. The production of ethanol suggests a shift in the carbon flux from the C4 to the C3 pathway. The origin of the shift in pathways is linked to the low concentration of CO₂ (~1.5 mM) in the fermentation medium [1,2] at the beginning of the stationary phase (Fig. 5, phase III). The decrease in the CO₂ solubility is linked with the opposite increase of k_{La} and Henry's constant for the presented fermentation process. The estimated values are respectively 23 h⁻¹ and 4142 kPa·L/mol (Supporting material; Eq. 1). The calculated Henry's constant is higher compared to the literature value for pure water at 310 K, reported for CO₂ at 3989 kPa·L/mol [4]. The increase in the estimated constant is a consequence of the negative effect of salts in the studied media and substrate solution. Moreover, the reported value for Henry's constant is in line with other studies performing succinic acid fermentation with *Actinobacillus succinogenes*, where the studied Henry's constant was 4116 kPa·L/mol [4,15]. As well as Henry's constant value, the k_{La} of the system respects the assumptions presented. The value calculated (23 h⁻¹) is strictly dependent on the operational condition of the reactor and its estimation is difficult. When the k_{La} is compared with literature, the authors can notice an increase respect to reported values for water solution (~1–3 h⁻¹), but a comparable estimation when reactors with similar configuration are taken into consideration (~16–20 h⁻¹) [30,31]. Further analysis on CO₂ equilibrium in the liquid media is presented in Supporting materials, section 1.1. A decrease of the inorganic carbon through the C4 pathway causes a decrease in the overall yield of SA production. Besides, a small amount of lactic acid was detected.

3.4. Inorganic carbon availability

Inorganic carbon availability is of major importance for SA fermentation since CO₂ is required for the production of SA (Supporting material, Eq. 5). Several studies present the effect of CO₂ during the fermentation process, however, no dissolved CO₂ profiles were

Fig. 4. Fermentative products and sugars consumption profile with 1 atm (A-B), 1.4 atm (C-D), and 1.6 atm (E-F). Succinic acid (■), Acetic acid (●) and Formic acid (◆). Ethanol (▲) and Lactic acid (▼) were detected in small amount. Sugars profile is described as follow: total sugars (△), maltose (∇), glucose (◇), and sucrose (◐).

Table 2
Sugars composition of sugars-rich industrial waste.

	Glucose (g/L)	Sucrose (g/L)	Maltose (g/L)	Total sugars (g/L)
Sugars-rich industrial waste 1	52.9 ± 4.9	19.6 ± 3.3	224.6 ± 4.5	306.9 ± 5.7
Sugars-rich industrial waste 2	46.6 ± 0.3	76.9 ± 5.6	152.9 ± 7.4	276.6 ± 2.7

previously reported in the literature. Usually, the CO₂ is estimated from alkaline neutralization or headspace gas composition [2,15]. Fig. 5 described the measured concentration of the CO₂ in the medium along with the cells' growth. A similar trend was observed for all the pressures applied (Fig. 5A, B, C). In total, five different phases can be distinguished from the inoculation time until the end of the fermentation, which are discussed below:

1. Phase I (0 – 2 h): during this period CO₂ dissolved increased from 1.4 to 8.1 mM. When no other factors influence the dissolution of the CO₂, the profile follows Henry's law and will attain the saturation point (C*s) according to the specific partial pressure (Figs. 5, 7.7 mM,

Table 3CH₄ and CO₂ profile at times 0 h and 24 h when different pressure was applied.

Time (h)	0.0		24	
Pressure (atm)	Methane (% v/v)	Carbon dioxide (% v/v)	Methane (% v/v)	Carbon dioxide (% v/v)
1.0	60.3 ± 1.3	39.7 ± 0.6	66.1 ± 0.9	33.8 ± 0.9
1.4	61.8 ± 4.2	38.2 ± 4.2	80.4 ± 2.6	19.6 ± 2.6
1.6	59.1 ± 3.3	40.8 ± 3.3	82.7 ± 7.4	17.3 ± 5.6

Fig. 5. CO₂ profile during fermentation for Succinic acid production. Dissolved CO₂ was analyzed at 1 atm (A), 1.4 atm (B), and 1.6 atm (C). Saturation concentrations at each pressure tested are shown as dash line in each profile as C*_{CO2} 1 atm (—), 1.4 atm (---) and 1.6 atm (---). Growth curves are presented as 1 atm (●), 1.4 atm (●) and 1.6 atm (●).

10.2 mM, 12.5 mM). When no microbial activity is present to consume CO₂, this will accumulate in the fermentation media. However, none of the profiles reached the saturation point (Fig. 5) due to microbial uptake. The difference between the CO₂ levels detected is based on the balance between the dissolution of CO₂ from the gas to the liquid phase and the CO₂ consumption by microbial activity in the early growth after inoculation. Increasing the pressure corresponds to a higher dissolved CO₂ available at the beginning of the fermentation (Fig. 5, 0–2 h). Since the only factor affecting CO₂ consumption in the medium is the biochemical reaction, higher utilization of the inorganic carbon occurred in the first stages of the fermentation at 1.4 and 1.6 atm (Fig. 5, 0–2 h). However, in all the profiles, the accumulation of CO₂ was still higher than the biomass consumption rate and the bacteria still did not uptake all the dissolved CO₂. Cells were growing in a rich carbon source environment

that could improve biomass formation and consequently SA production.

- Phase II (2.0 – 3.0 h): the CO₂ consumption rate increased due to the occurrence of the exponential phase for the biomass in the medium. As result, all three profiles of dissolved CO₂ reached a maximum at 2.0 h of fermentation. Afterward, in all the three CO₂ profiles, the consumption rate overcame the accumulation rate and therefore the concentration started to decrease. This condition where the inorganic carbon is directly consumed is influenced by the biomass concentration, sugar availability, and operational condition (e.g. mixing speed and headspace partial pressure).
- Phase III (3.0 – 7.5 h): when the microbial uptake becomes higher compared to the accumulation in the medium, the system enters into the consumption phase (Figs. 5, 3h). CO₂ concentration decreased quickly suggesting that the CO₂ dissolution rate was lower compared to the CO₂ uptake rate. The rate of sugar consumption (-r_s) followed the -r_{CO2} profile further supporting that the CO₂ consumption was related to microbial activity catalyzing CO₂ to the products.
- Phase IV (7.5–15 h): a decrease in CO₂ consumption rate (-r_{CO2}) was observed. The biomass profile indicates the beginning of the stationary phase with the consequent reduction of CO₂ uptake by the bacteria. During this period the level of inorganic carbon was at its minimum (0.80 mM Fig. 5A; 0.68 mM Fig. 5B; 0.65 mM Fig. 5C) as well as by-products formation (Fig. 3, A, C, E). A slight decrease in the dissolved concentration was detected in all three profiles until a minimum is reached. It is possible to notice that when the pressure increase, the minimum is delayed from 9.0 h at 1.0 atm (Figs. 5A, 9.0 h) to 15.0 h at 1.6 atm (Figs. 5C, 15.0 h). Then, the concentration starts increasing suggesting a decrease in microbial consumption. Operating the system at a higher pressure can lead to a higher dissolution of the inorganic substrate and consequently avoid that the profile achieves limiting dissolved concentration in the medium.
- Phase V (15.0 – 24.0 h): when fermentation reached 14 h, the last phase for dissolved CO₂ was quantified. The accumulation leads again to the dissolution equilibrium of the gas since -r_{CO2} became neglectable. As a result, a new saturation point was then reached at a lower concentration compared to the beginning of the fermentation, i.e. 8.16 mM for 1.0 atm, 6.62 mM for 1.4 atm, and 3.67 mM for 1.6 atm (Fig. 5, 23–24 h). Consequently, no consumption is taking place, and as well as no production of SA as indicated in Fig. 4.

3.5. Impact of pressure

The 1.0 atm headspace pressure reached the nearest value referred to as the saturation point, instead the pressurized system demonstrated a higher consumption of both organic and inorganic carbon sources in the first hours of fermentation.

The effect of pressure is particularly evident in phase III. When the dissolved CO₂ concentrations at different pressures are compared, it is possible to notice a higher CO₂ concentration in the medium when the pressure increases (Fig. 5). At 5 h, the concentration detected for 1.4 and 1.6 atm are 4.8 and 5.1 mM, 30% higher compared to 1 atm (Figs. 5, 5h) with the consequent higher availability to the bacteria during the exponential phase. The CO₂ fixation rate confirmed the previous assumption: the increase in pressure corresponds to a higher fixation rate. At 1.0 atm, the titer of succinic acid reached 20.3 ± 1.3 g/L with the fixation of 0.15 mol of CO₂ per mol of SA. However, at 1.4 and 1.6 atm, a fixation of 0.19 and 0.18 mol in the final products was quantified. As consequence, both a higher consumption of gas was detected, as well as the yield raised from 0.48 ± 0.03 g/g to 0.64 ± 0.06 and 0.65 ± 0.09 g/g for 1.4 and 1.6 atm systems. Besides, at 1.0 atm, the fixation capacity achieved only 0.128 L_{CO2}·h⁻¹ compare to 0.296 L_{CO2}·h⁻¹ at 1.4 atm (p < 0.05). Similarly, at 1.6 the total amount of CO₂ fixed was respectively at 0.342 L_{CO2}·h⁻¹ (p < 0.05). Overall, at 1.0 atm the system was able to fix 0.07 L of CO₂ per liter of medium (L_{CO2}·L_(l) h⁻¹) and a significant increase was further notice when

compare with 1.4 atm ($0.16 L_{CO_2} \cdot L_{(l)}^{-1} \cdot h^{-1}$; $p < 0.05$) and with 1.6 atm ($0.19 L_{CO_2} \cdot L_{(l)}^{-1} \cdot h^{-1}$; $p < 0.05$).

The authors can evidence a higher CO_2 fixation based on biomass produced at 1.6 atm ($0.056 g_{CO_2}/g_{CDW} h^{-1}$) and 1.4 atm ($0.043 g_{CO_2}/g_{CDW} h^{-1}$) compared to 1.0 ($0.026 g_{CO_2}/g_{CDW} h^{-1}$; $p < 0.05$). Nevertheless, SA production was higher at 1.4 atm, then suggesting the utilization of CO_2 for biomass production instead of SA formation. From a commercial perspective, a particular interest must be given to the CO_2 fixation capacity of the fermentation process. At the lab scale, a maximum of 0.342 L of CO_2 was fixed per hour of fermentation. When the presented fermentation is compared with other CO_2 fixation processes, such as microalgae cultivation or chemical removal [37,38], better performance is achieved. In the present study, a fixation of 0.7 g of CO_2 per gram of cells formed was reached, instead, Chae et al. [39] were able to fix 0.4 g of CO_2 per gram of cells in a bioreactor for single-cell proteins. It is important to remember that in the present investigation, CO_2 fixation is linked with both the production of an added-value product (SA) and the simultaneous consumption of a waste outcome from the food industrial sector. As result, providing CO_2 from biogas plants to SA fermentation could further increase competitiveness against the petrochemical-based market both by decreasing downstream cost for salts ($MgCO_3$, $NaHCO_3$, etc.) removal and second by producing high in purity bio-methane.

4. Conclusions

The study proves the successful use of sugars-rich industrial waste and CO_2/CH_4 gas mixture for biosuccinic acid production. In the present research, the profile of dissolved CO_2 is systematically described to elucidate its role during succinic acid production. Five different phases are discussed for the CO_2 dissolved profile when biomass generation, product formation, and substrate consumption regulate the CO_2 availability. In particular, phase I to phase III (from 0 h to 7.5 h) are critical to improve the CO_2 fixation capacity of the process based on microbial consumption. Adjusting the CO_2 concentration on the microbial growth in batch operation can avoid waste of gas in open systems and increase the CO_2 fixation rate with the consequent higher methane upgrade capacity in recirculated operations. Finally, increasing CO_2 pressure corresponds to an improvement in performance parameters such as yield and productivity as well as a higher fixation capacity.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Francesco Vigato: Conceptualization, Investigation, Validation, Formal analysis, Data Curation, Writing – original draft. **Irini Angelidaki:** Conceptualization, Project administration, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Supervision. **John M. Woodley:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Merlin Alvarado-Morales:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Resources, Data curation, Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Supervision.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research And Innovation Program Neosuccess under grant

agreement No (950921) and by the H2020-Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions AgRefine Project under the grant agreement No (860477), and ACT ERA-NET Cofund under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program (Project No 327331 CooCE, Grant Agreement 862087) co-funded by EUDP (No 64021.2006).

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.bej.2022.108602](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2022.108602).

References

- [1] M.J. Van Der Werf, M.V. Guettler, M.K. Jain, J.G. Zeikus, Environmental and physiological factors affecting the succinate product ratio during carbohydrate fermentation by *Actinobacillus* sp. 130Z, *Arch. Microbiol.* 167 (1997) 332–342, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s002030050452>.
- [2] J. Herselman, M.F.A. Bradfield, U. Vijayan, W. Nicol, The effect of carbon dioxide availability on succinic acid production with biofilms of *Actinobacillus succinogenes*, *Biochem. Eng. J.* 117 (2017) 218–225, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2016.10.018>.
- [3] W. Dessie, F. Xin, W. Zhang, Y. Jiang, H. Wu, J. Ma, M. Jiang, Opportunities, challenges, and future perspectives of succinic acid production by *Actinobacillus succinogenes*, *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 102 (2018) 9893–9910, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00253-018-9379-5>.
- [4] Y.L. Xi, K.Q. Chen, J. Li, X.J. Fang, X.Y. Zheng, S.S. Sui, M. Jiang, P. Wei, Optimization of culture conditions in CO_2 fixation for succinic acid production using *Actinobacillus succinogenes*, *J. Ind. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 38 (2011) 1605–1612, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10295-011-0952-5>.
- [5] M. Aresta, A. Dibenedetto, A. Angelini, Catalysis for the valorization of exhaust carbon: From CO_2 to chemicals, materials, and fuels. technological use of CO_2 , *Chem. Rev.* 114 (2014) 1709–1742, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr4002758>.
- [6] J.B. Holm-Nielsen, T. Al Seadi, P. Oleskowicz-Popiel, The future of anaerobic digestion and biogas utilization, *Bioreour. Technol.* 100 (2009) 5478–5484, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2008.12.046>.
- [7] K.-K. Cheng, X.-B. Zhao, J. Zeng, J.-A. Zhang, Biotechnological production of succinic acid: current state and perspectives, *Biofuels Bioprod. Bioref.* 6 (2012) 302–318, <https://doi.org/10.1002/bbb.1327>.
- [8] Q. Li, D. Wang, Z. Song, W. Zhou, Y. Wu, J. Xing, Z. Su, Dual-phase fermentation enables *Actinobacillus succinogenes* 130ZT to be a potential role for high-level lactate production from the bioresour, *Bioreour. Technol.* 101 (2010) 7665–7667, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2010.04.058>.
- [9] A. Rigaki, C. Webb, C. Theodoropoulos, Double substrate limitation model for the bio-based production of succinic acid from glycerol, *Biochem. Eng. J.* 153 (2020), 107391, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2019.107391>.
- [10] H. Almqvist, C. Pateraki, M. Alexandri, A. Koutinas, G. Lidén, Succinic acid production by *Actinobacillus succinogenes* from batch fermentation of mixed sugars, *J. Ind. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 43 (2016) 1117–1130, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10295-016-1787-x>.
- [11] M.F.A. Bradfield, W. Nicol, Continuous succinic acid production by *Actinobacillus succinogenes* in a biofilm reactor: Steady-state metabolic flux variation, *Biochem. Eng. J.* 85 (2014) 1–7, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2014.01.009>.
- [12] W. Zou, L.W. Zhu, H.M. Li, Y.J. Tang, Significance of CO_2 donor on the production of succinic acid by *Actinobacillus succinogenes* ATCC 55618, *Microb. Cell Fact.* 10 (2011) 1–10, <https://doi.org/10.1186/1475-2859-10-87>.
- [13] C.D. van Heerden, W. Nicol, Continuous succinic acid fermentation by *Actinobacillus succinogenes*, *Biochem. Eng. J.* 73 (2013) 5–11, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2013.01.015>.
- [14] H. Song, W.L. Jeong, S. Choi, K.Y. Jong, H.H. Won, S.Y. Lee, Effects of dissolved CO_2 levels on the growth of *mannheimia succiniciproducens* and succinic acid production, *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* 98 (2007) 1296–1304, <https://doi.org/10.1002/bit.21530>.
- [15] I.B. Gunnarsson, M. Alvarado-Morales, I. Angelidaki, Utilization of CO_2 fixing bacterium *Actinobacillus succinogenes* 130Z for simultaneous biogas upgrading and biosuccinic acid production, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 48 (2014) 12464–12468, <https://doi.org/10.1021/es504000h>.
- [16] M. Bradfield, W. Nicol, J. Herselman, M.F.A. Bradfield, U. Vijayan, W. Nicol, The effect of carbon dioxide availability on succinic acid production with biofilms of *Actinobacillus succinogenes* the effect of carbon dioxide availability on succinic acid production with biofilms of *Actinobacillus succinogenes*, *Biochem. Eng. J.* 117 (2016) 218–225, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2016.10.018>.
- [17] G.S. Marinho, M. Alvarado-Morales, I. Angelidaki, Valorization of macroalga *Saccharina latissima* as novel feedstock for fermentation-based succinic acid production in a biorefinery approach and economic aspects, *Algal Res.* 16 (2016) 102–109, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.algal.2016.02.023>.
- [18] M. Babaei, P. Tsapekos, M. Alvarado-Morales, M. Hosseini, S. Ebrahimi, A. Niaei, I. Angelidaki, Valorization of organic waste with simultaneous biogas upgrading for the production of succinic acid, *Biochem. Eng. J.* 147 (2019) 136–145, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2019.04.012>.
- [19] D. Ladakis, E. Stylianou, S.M. Ioannidou, A. Koutinas, C. Pateraki, Biorefinery development, techno-economic evaluation and environmental impact analysis for the conversion of the organic fraction of municipal solid waste into succinic acid

- and value-added fractions, *Bioresour. Technol.* 354 (2022), 127172, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2022.127172>.
- [20] M. Kuglarz, M. Alvarado-Morales, K. Dąbkowska, I. Angelidaki, Integrated production of cellulosic bioethanol and succinic acid from rapeseed straw after dilute-acid pretreatment, *Bioresour. Technol.* 265 (2018) 191–199, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2018.05.099>.
- [21] T. Raj, K. Chandrasekhar, A. Naresh Kumar, J. Rajesh Banu, J.J. Yoon, S. Kant Bhatia, Y.H. Yang, S. Varjani, S.H. Kim, Recent advances in commercial biorefineries for lignocellulosic ethanol production: current status, challenges and future perspectives, *Bioresour. Technol.* 344 (2022), 126292, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2021.126292>.
- [22] C. Chenebault, R. Moscoviz, E. Trably, R. Escudié, B. Percheron, Lactic acid production from food waste using a microbial consortium: focus on key parameters for process upscaling and fermentation residues valorization, *Bioresour. Technol.* 354 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2022.127230>.
- [23] G. Su, C. Chan, J. He, Enhanced biobutanol production from starch waste via orange peel doping, *Renew. Energy* 193 (2022) 576–583, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2022.04.096>.
- [24] C. Zhang, T. Li, G. Su, J. He, Enhanced direct fermentation from food waste to butanol and hydrogen by an amylolytic *Clostridium*, *Renew. Energy* 153 (2020) 522–529, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2020.01.151>.
- [25] H. Wang, C.W. Tsang, M.H. To, G. Kaur, S.L.K.W. Roelants, C.V. Stevens, W. Soetaert, C.S.K. Lin, Techno-economic evaluation of a biorefinery applying food waste for sophorolipid production – A case study for Hong Kong, *Bioresour. Technol.* 303 (2020), 122852, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2020.122852>.
- [26] N. Lawson, M. Alvarado-Morales, P. Tsapekos, I. Angelidaki, Techno-economic assessment of biological biogas upgrading based on danish biogas plants, *Energies* 14 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14248252>.
- [27] J. Li, M. Jiang, K. Chen, L. Shang, P. Wei, H. Ying, Q. Ye, P. Ouyang, H. Chang, Enhanced production of succinic acid by *Actinobacillus succinogenes* with reductive carbon source, *Process Biochem.* 45 (2010) 980–985, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procbio.2010.03.001>.
- [28] M.P. Dorado, S.K.C. Lin, A. Koutinas, C. Du, R. Wang, C. Webb, Cereal-based biorefinery development: utilisation of wheat milling by-products for the production of succinic acid, *J. Biotechnol.* 143 (2009) 51–59, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiotec.2009.06.009>.
- [29] M. Ferone, F. Raganati, G. Olivieri, A. Marzocchella, Bioreactors for succinic acid production processes, *Crit. Rev. Biotechnol.* 39 (2019) 571–586, <https://doi.org/10.1080/07388551.2019.1592105>.
- [30] P. Talbot, M.P. Gortares, R.W. Lencki, J. de la Noüe, Absorption of CO₂ in algal mass culture systems: a different characterization approach, *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* 37 (1991) 834–842, <https://doi.org/10.1002/bit.260370907>.
- [31] B. Le Gouic, H. Marec, J. Pruvost, J.F. Cornet, Investigation of growth limitation by CO₂ mass transfer and inorganic carbon source for the microalga *Chlorella vulgaris* in a dedicated photobioreactor, *Chem. Eng. Sci.* 233 (2021), 116388, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ces.2020.116388>.
- [32] C. Pateraki, M. Patsalou, A. Vlysidis, N. Kopsahelis, C. Webb, A.A. Koutinas, M. Koutinas, *Actinobacillus succinogenes*: advances on succinic acid production and prospects for development of integrated biorefineries, *Biochem. Eng. J.* 112 (2016) 285–303, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2016.04.005>.
- [33] J.B. McKinlay, M. Laivenieks, B.D. Schindler, A.A. McKinlay, S. Siddaramappa, J. F. Challacombe, S.R. Lowry, A. Clum, A.L. Lapidus, K.B. Burkhart, V. Harkins, C. Vieille, A genomic perspective on the potential of *Actinobacillus succinogenes* for industrial succinate production, *BMC Genom.* 11 (2010), <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2164-11-680>.
- [34] R.N. Goldberg, Y.B. Tewari, J.C. Ahluwalia, Thermodynamics of the hydrolysis of sucrose, *J. Biol. Chem.* 264 (1989) 9901–9904, [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0021-9258\(18\)81744-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0021-9258(18)81744-6).
- [35] Y.B. Tewari, R.N. Goldberg, Thermodynamics of hydrolysis of disaccharides, *J. Biol. Chem.* 264 (1989) 3966–3971, [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0021-9258\(18\)84947-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0021-9258(18)84947-5).
- [36] K. Amulya, H. Kopperi, S. Venkata Mohan, Tunable production of succinic acid at elevated pressures of CO₂ in a high pressure gas fermentation reactor, *Bioresour. Technol.* 309 (2020), 123327, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2020.123327>.
- [37] T.E. Rufford, S. Smart, G.C.Y. Watson, B.F. Graham, J. Boxall, J.C. Diniz da Costa, E.F. May, The removal of CO₂ and N₂ from natural gas: a review of conventional and emerging process technologies, *J. Pet. Sci. Eng.* 94–95 (2012) 123–154, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.petrol.2012.06.016>.
- [38] A. Kumar, S. Ergas, X. Yuan, A. Sahu, Q. Zhang, J. Dewulf, F.X. Malcata, H. van Langenhove, Enhanced CO₂ fixation and biofuel production via microalgae: Recent developments and future directions, *Trends Biotechnol.* 28 (2010) 371–380, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tibtech.2010.04.004>.
- [39] S.R. Chae, E.J. Hwang, H.S. Shin, Single cell protein production of *Euglena gracilis* and carbon dioxide fixation in an innovative photo-bioreactor, *Bioresour. Technol.* 97 (2006) 322–329, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2005.02.037>.